

ROUGH APPROXIMATIONS OF INTERVAL ROUGH FUZZY IDEALS IN GAMMA-SEMIGROUPS

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we introduce the notions of interval rough fuzzy Γ -ideals, bi- Γ -ideal, prime- Γ - ideal and prime-bi- Γ -ideal in Γ -semigroup and establish some interesting properties of these structures.

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1965, the concept of fuzzy sets was introduced by Zadeh[10] and paved the way to study uncertainty problems. Applications of fuzzy set theory have been found in various fields. Sen [7] defined the Γ -semigroup in 1986. The notion of rough set was introduced by Pawlak[4] as a new tool for reasoning about data. Rough set theory is a powerful tool to deal with imperfect data. The rough set theory is an extension of set theory. The main idea of rough set corresponds to the concepts of lower and upper approximations of a set. The lower approximation of a given set is the union of all equivalence classes which are subsets of the set, and the upper approximation is the union of all equivalence classes which have a nonempty intersection with the set. Zadeh[9] introduced the notion of interval-valued fuzzy sets as a generalization of fuzzy sets in 1975, i.e., a fuzzy subset with an interval-valued membership function. Later by combining rough sets and fuzzy sets, the notion of rough fuzzy sets were introduced by Dubois and Prade [2] in 1990. The notion of interval valued rough fuzzy sets in semigroups was introduced by Subha et al.[5].

Throughout this paper let us denote S as Γ -semigroup, ∂ as complete congruence relation and Ω as interval valued fuzzy set.

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this section we list some concepts that are required in the development of our work.

Definition 2.1. Let S be a Γ semigroup and ∂ congruence relation on S . The pair (S, ∂) is called an approximation space. Let Ω be any nonempty subset of S . The sets

$$\partial^l(\Omega) = \{x \in S/[x]_{\partial} \subseteq \Omega\} \text{ and } \partial^u(\Omega) = \{x \in S/[x]_{\partial} \cap \Omega \neq \phi\}$$

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are called the lower and upper approximations of Ω . Then $\partial(\Omega) = (\partial^l(\Omega), \partial^u(\Omega))$ is called rough set in (S, ∂) .

Definition 2.2. Let Ω be a fuzzy subset of S . The fuzzy subsets of S defined by

$$\partial^u(\Omega)(x) = \bigvee_{a \in [x]_{\partial}} \Omega(a) \text{ and } \partial^l(\Omega)(x) = \bigwedge_{a \in [x]_{\partial}} \Omega(a)$$

are called respectively, the upper and lower approximations of the fuzzy set Ω . $\partial(\Omega) = (\partial^l(\Omega), \partial^u(\Omega))$ is called a rough fuzzy set of Ω with respect to ∂ if $\partial^l(\Omega) \neq \partial^u(\Omega)$.

Definition 2.3. Let Ω be an *IF* subset of S and $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$, we call $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]) = \{x \in X : \Omega^-(x) \geq \lambda_1, \Omega^+(x) \geq \lambda_2\}$ and $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)) = \{x \in X : \Omega^-(x) > \lambda_1, \Omega^+(x) > \lambda_2\}$ the $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2]$ - level set of Ω and (λ_1, λ_2) - level set of A , respectively.

Let S be the finite and nonempty set called the universe and assume that S is a Γ -semigroup. Let Ω be an *IF* subset of S and let ∂ be the complete congruence relation on S . Let $\partial^l(\Omega)$ and $\partial^u(\Omega)$ be the *IF* subset of S defined by,

$$\begin{aligned} \partial^l(\Omega)(x) &= [\wedge \Omega^-(y); y \in [x]_{\partial}, \wedge \Omega^+(y); y \in [x]_{\partial}] \\ \partial^u(\Omega)(x) &= [\vee \Omega^-(y); y \in [x]_{\partial}, \vee \Omega^+(y); y \in [x]_{\partial}] \end{aligned}$$

Then $\partial(\Omega) = (\partial^l(\Omega), \partial^u(\Omega))$ is called an *IRF* set if $\partial^l(\Omega) \neq \partial^u(\Omega)$.

Theorem 2.1. [5] *Let ∂ be a congruence relation on S . If Ω is an IF subset of S and $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$, then*

- (i) $(\partial^l(\Omega), [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]) = \partial^l(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$
- (ii) $(\partial^u(\Omega), (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)) = \partial^u(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$.

Theorem 2.2. [8] *Let ∂ be a complete congruence on S and Ω prime ideal of S . Then the following statements are true.*

- (i) *If $\partial^l(\Omega) \neq \phi$, then Ω is a ∂ -lower rough prime ideal of S .*
- (ii) *Ω is a ∂ -upper rough prime ideal of S .*

3. INTERVAL ROUGH FUZZY Γ -IDEALS, INTERVAL ROUGH FUZZY BI- Γ -IDEAL AND INTERVAL ROUGH FUZZY SUB- Γ -SEMIGROUP (*IRFgI*, *IRFBgI* AND *IRFSgS*)

In this section we introduce the concept of *IRF* set of S . We also introduce the concept of *IRFgI*, *IRFSgS* and *IRFBgI* of S . Example of *IRFgI* is discussed. An *IF* subset of S is called an *IRFgI* of S if it is both upper and lower *IRFgI* of S .

Theorem 3.1. *If Ω is an IFgI of S , then $\partial^u(\Omega)$ is an IFgI of S .*

Proof. Assume that Ω is an *IF* left *gI* of S , then for all $x, y \in S$, we have $\Omega(x\gamma y) \geq \Omega(y)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \partial^u(\Omega)(x\gamma y) &= \bigvee_{p\gamma q \in [x\gamma y]_{\partial}} \Omega(p\gamma q) \\ &\geq \bigvee_{\substack{p \in [x]_{\partial} \\ \gamma q \in [y]_{\partial}}} \Omega(p\gamma q) \\ &\geq \bigvee_{\substack{q \in [y]_{\partial}}} \Omega(q) \\ &= \partial^u(\Omega)(y) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\partial^u(\Omega)$ is an *IFgI* of S . □

Theorem 3.2. *If Ω is an IFgI of S , then $\partial^u(\Omega)$ is an IFgI of S .*

Proof. Similar to 3.1. □

Theorem 3.3. *If Ω is an IFgI of S , then $\partial^u(\Omega)$ is IRFgI of S .*

Proof. By applying Theorems 3.1 and 3.2 we get the result. □

Example 3.1. Let $S = \{e, a, b\}$ be a Γ -semigroup and $\Gamma = \{\gamma\}$ with the following multiplication table

γ	e	a	b
e	e	e	e
a	e	a	e
b	e	e	b

Let ∂ be a complete congruence relation S and the equivalence classes of S are $\{\{e\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Also an IF subset of S are defined by $\Omega(e) = [1, 1]$, $\Omega(a) = [.8, .9]$ and $\Omega(b) = [.7, .8]$. Then Ω is an IRFgI of S .

Theorem 3.4. *Let Ω be an IF subset of S . Then Ω is an IFgI of S if and only if for all $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$ then $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ (resp., $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)) \neq \phi, (\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$) is a gI of S .*

Proof. Let us assume that Ω is an IFgI of S . Assume $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]) \neq \phi$.

Let $x \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$, $y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Then $\Omega(x) \geq [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]$. Since Ω is an IFgI of S then $\Omega(x\gamma y) \geq \Omega(x) \wedge \Omega(y) \geq [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]$ implies $x\gamma y \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$. Similarly $y\gamma x \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$. Hence $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is an gI of S .

Conversely, let us take $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$ if $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]) \neq \phi$, then $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is an gI of S . Let $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Then we have two cases

Case(I): If $\Omega(x) \leq \Omega(y)$ and let $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] = \Omega(x)$. Then $x \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$.

By assumption $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is an gI of S . So $x\gamma y \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$. Then

$$\Omega(x\gamma y) \geq [\lambda_1, \lambda_2] = \Omega(x) = \Omega(x) \wedge \Omega(y).$$

Case(II): If $\Omega(x) \geq \Omega(y)$. Let $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] = \Omega(y)$. Then $y \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$.

By assumption we've $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is an gI of S . So $x\gamma y \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$

$$\Omega(x\gamma y) \geq [\lambda_1, \lambda_2] = \Omega(y) = \Omega(x) \wedge \Omega(y).$$

Hence from Case(I) and Case(II) we have $\Omega(x\gamma y) \geq \Omega(x) \wedge \Omega(y)$. Therefore Ω is an IFgI of S . Similarly we prove for other case. □

Theorem 3.5. *Let Ω be an IFgI of S . Then $\partial^u(\Omega)$ is an IFgI of S .*

Proof. Assume that Ω is an IFgI of S . Let $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$ then

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(x\gamma y) &\geq \Omega(x) \vee \Omega(y). \\ \partial^u(\Omega)(x\gamma y) &= \bigvee_{a \in [x\gamma y]_{\partial}} \Omega(a) \\ &= \bigvee_{a \in [x]_{\partial} \gamma [y]_{\partial}} \Omega(a) \\ &= \bigvee_{c \in [x]_{\partial} d \in [y]_{\partial}} \Omega(c\gamma d) \\ &\geq \left(\bigvee_{c \in [x]_{\partial}} \Omega(c) \right) \wedge \left(\bigvee_{d \in [y]_{\partial}} \Omega(d) \right) \\ &= \partial^u(\Omega)(x) \wedge \partial^u(\Omega)(y). \end{aligned}$$

Hence the theorem. □

An IF subset of S is called an IRF sub- Γ -semigroup of S if it is both upper and lower IRF sub- Γ -semigroup of S .

Theorem 3.6. *If Ω is an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S , then $\partial^u(\Omega)$ is an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S .*

Proof. Assume that Ω is an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S . Let $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Then $\Omega(x\gamma y) \geq \Omega(x) \wedge \Omega(y)$

$$\begin{aligned} \partial^u(\Omega)(x\gamma y) &= \bigvee_{p\gamma q \in [x\gamma y]_{\partial}} \Omega(p\gamma q) \\ &\geq \bigvee_{p \in [x]_{\partial} \gamma q \in [y]_{\partial}} (\Omega(p\gamma q)) \\ &\geq \bigvee_{p \in [x]_{\partial} \gamma q \in [y]_{\partial}} (\Omega(p) \wedge \Omega(q)) \\ &\geq \left(\bigvee_{p \in [x]_{\partial}} \Omega(p) \right) \wedge \left(\bigvee_{q \in [y]_{\partial}} \Omega(q) \right) \\ &= \partial^u(\Omega)(x) \wedge \partial^u(\Omega)(y) \end{aligned}$$

This proves that $\partial^u(\Omega)$ is an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S . Similarly we can prove for lower approximation. □

Theorem 3.7. *If Ω is an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S , then $\partial^l(\Omega)$ is an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S .*

By combining Theorem 3.6 and Theorem 3.7 we get the following theorem.

Theorem 3.8. *Let Ω be an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S . Then Ω is an IRF sub- Γ -semigroup of S .*

Theorem 3.9. *Let Ω be an IF subset of S then Ω is an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S if and only if $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$ is a sub- Γ -semigroup of S for all $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$.*

Proof. Suppose Ω is an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S . Let $x, y \in (\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$ then

$$\Omega(x) > (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \text{ and } \Omega(y) > (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \text{ implies } \Omega(x\gamma y) > (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)$$

Thus $x\gamma y \in (\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$. Hence $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$ is a sub- Γ -semigroup of S .

Conversely, suppose that $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$ is a sub- Γ -semigroup of S for each $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$. For any $x, y \in S$, and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Let

$$\Omega(x) = [\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \text{ and } \Omega(y) = [\lambda_3, \lambda_4].$$

Then $\Omega(x) = (\lambda_1, \lambda_2) > (\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_3, \lambda_2 \wedge \lambda_4)$ and $\Omega(y) = (\lambda_3, \lambda_4) > (\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_3, \lambda_2 \wedge \lambda_4)$.

Thus $x, y \in (\Omega, (\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_3, \lambda_2 \wedge \lambda_4))$, since $(\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_3, \lambda_2 \wedge \lambda_4) \in D[0, 1]$. By hypothesis $x\gamma y \in (\Omega, (\lambda_1 \wedge \lambda_3, \lambda_2 \wedge \lambda_4))$. Hence Ω is an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S . □

Theorem 3.10. *Let Ω be an IF subset of S then Ω is an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S if and only if $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a sub- Γ -semigroup of S for all $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$.*

Theorem 3.11. *If Ω is an $IFBgI$ of S , then $\partial^u(\Omega)$ is an $IFBgI$ of S .*

Proof. Assume that Ω is an $IFBgI$ of S . Then $\Omega(x\beta s\gamma y) \geq \Omega(x) \wedge \Omega(y)$ for all $x, y, s \in S$ and $\beta, \gamma \in \Gamma$.

$$\begin{aligned} \partial^u(\Omega)(x\beta s\gamma y) &= \bigvee_{r \in [x\beta s\gamma y]_{\partial}} \Omega(r) \\ &= \bigvee_{r \in [x]_{\partial} \beta [s]_{\partial} \gamma [y]_{\partial}} \Omega(r) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \bigvee_{pqt \in [x]_{\partial} \beta [s]_{\partial} \gamma [y]_{\partial}} \Omega(p\beta q\gamma t) \\
&\geq \bigvee_{p \in [x]_{\partial} t \in [y]_{\partial}} [(\Omega(p) \wedge \Omega(t))] \\
&= \partial^u(\Omega)(x) \wedge \partial^u(\Omega)(y)
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

From equation (1) and by Theorem 3.1 we obtain $\partial^u(\Omega)$ is an *IFBgI* of S . \square

Theorem 3.12. *If Ω is an IFBgI of S , then $\partial^l(\Omega)$ is an IFBgI of S .*

Theorem 3.13. *Let Ω be an IF subset of S . If Ω is an IFBgI of S , then Ω is an IRFBgI of S .*

Proof. Follows from Theorem 3.11 and 3.12 \square

Theorem 3.14. *An IF subset of S is an IFBgI of S if and only if $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$ is a BgI of S for all $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$.*

Proof. Suppose that Ω is an IFBgI of S . Let $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$. Then Ω is an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S . By Theorem 3.9 $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$ is a sub- Γ -semigroup of S . Let $t \in (\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)) \Gamma S \Gamma (\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)), y \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$ such that $t = x\alpha y\beta z$. Since Ω is an IFBgI, $\Omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \Omega(x) \wedge \Omega(z) > (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)$ implies $t \in (\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$.

Thus $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)) \Gamma S \Gamma (\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)) \subseteq (\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$. Hence $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$ is a BgI of S . Conversely, suppose that $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$ is a BgI of S , then $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$ is sub- Γ -semigroup of S . By Theorem 3.9 Ω is an IF sub- Γ -semigroup of S . For any $x, z \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. Let $\Omega(x) = [\lambda_3, \lambda_4]$ and $\Omega(z) = [\lambda_5, \lambda_6]$ then $x, z \in (\Omega, (\lambda_3 \wedge \lambda_5, \lambda_4 \wedge \lambda_6))$. Let $y \in S$ then $x\alpha y\beta z \in (\Omega, (\lambda_3 \wedge \lambda_5, \lambda_4 \wedge \lambda_6))$ implies that $\Omega(x\alpha y\beta z) > (\lambda_3 \wedge \lambda_5, \lambda_4 \wedge \lambda_6) = \Omega(x) \wedge \Omega(z)$. Hence Ω is an IFBgI of S . \square

4. INTERVAL ROUGH FUZZY PRIME- Γ -IDEAL (IRFPgI)

In this section we introduce the concept of IRFPgI of S .

Theorem 4.1. *Let Ω be an IF subset of S . Then Ω is an IFPgI of S if and only if for all $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$, $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a PgI of S .*

Proof. Assume that Ω is an IFPgI of S . Then Ω is an IF an gI of S . Assume $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]) \neq \phi$. By Theorem 3.4 $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a gI of S . Let $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$ then $x\gamma y \in \Omega_{[\lambda_1, \lambda_2]}$. Since Ω is an IFPgI of S . $\Omega(x\gamma y) = \Omega(x)$ or $\Omega(x\gamma y) = \Omega(y)$ and $x \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ or $y \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ Therefore $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a PgI of S .

Conversely, assume that for all $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$, if $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]) \neq \phi$, then $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a PgI of S . Let $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. By Theorem 3.4 Ω is an IFgI of S . This implies $\Omega(x\gamma y) \geq \Omega(y)$ and $\Omega(x\gamma y) \geq \Omega(x)$. Let $\lambda_1 = \Omega(x\gamma y)$. Thus $x\gamma y \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$. Since $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a PgI of S , $x \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ or $y \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$. This implies that $\Omega(x) \geq [\lambda_1, \lambda_2] = \Omega(x\gamma y)$ or $\Omega(y) \geq [\lambda_1, \lambda_2] = \Omega(x\gamma y)$. Hence $\Omega(x\gamma y) = \Omega(x)$ or $\Omega(x\gamma y) = \Omega(y)$. Hence Ω is an IFPgI of S . \square

Theorem 4.2. *Let Ω be an IF subset of S . Then Ω is an IFPgI of S if and only if for all $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$, $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$ is a PgI of S .*

Theorem 4.3. *Let Ω be an IFPgI of S . Then Ω is an IRFPgI of S .*

Proof. By applying Theorems 3.4, 4.2, 2.1 and 2.2 we get the result. \square

5. INTERVAL ROUGH FUZZY PRIME-BI- Γ -IDEAL (*IRFPBgI*)

In this section we introduce the notion of *IRFPBgI* of S also discuss some property of this ideal.

Theorem 5.1. *Let Ω be an IF subset of S . Then Ω is an IFPBgI of S if and only if $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ (resp., $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)) \neq \phi$) is a PBgI of S for every $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$.*

Proof. Suppose that Ω is an IFPBgI of S . Then Ω is an IFBgI of S . Assume that $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]) \neq \phi$. By Theorem 3.14 $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a BgI of S . Let $x, y, a \in S$ and $\gamma, \beta \in \Gamma$ such that $x\gamma a\beta y \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$. Since Ω is an IFPBgI of S , we have $\Omega(x\gamma a\beta y) = \Omega(x)$ or $\Omega(x\gamma a\beta y) = \Omega(y)$. Thus $x \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ or $y \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$. Hence $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a PBgI of S .

Conversely, suppose that for all $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$, if $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]) \neq \phi$, and $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a PBgI of S . Let $x, a, y \in S$ and $\gamma, \beta \in \Gamma$. By Theorem 3.14 Ω is an IFPBgI of S . Then, we have $\Omega(x\gamma a\beta y) = \Omega(x) \wedge \Omega(y)$. Let $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] = \Omega(x\gamma a\beta y)$ and $x\gamma a\beta y \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$. Since $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a PBgI of S , we have $x \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ or $y \in (\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ which implies $\Omega(x) \geq [\lambda_1, \lambda_2] = \Omega(x\gamma a\beta y)$ or $\Omega(y) \geq [\lambda_1, \lambda_2] = \Omega(x\gamma a\beta y)$. Hence Ω is an IFPBgI of S . □

A nonempty set IF set Ω is called an *IRFPBgI* of S if it is both lower and upper *IRFPBgI* of S .

Theorem 5.2. *Let Ω be an IFPBgI of S . Then Ω is an IRFPBgI of S .*

Theorem 5.3. *Let Ω be an IFPBgI of S . Then Ω is a ∂ -lower IRFPBgI of S if and only if for all $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$ $\partial(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]) \neq \phi$, and $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a ∂ -lower rough PBgI of S .*

Proof. Suppose that Ω is a ∂ -lower IRFPBgI of S . $\partial(\Omega)$ is a IFPBgI of S . By Theorem 5.1 $(\partial(\Omega), [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a PBgI of S . By Theorem 2.1 $\partial(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2]) = (\partial(\Omega), [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ and this implies $\partial(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a PBgI of S . Hence $(\Omega, [\lambda_1, \lambda_2])$ is a ∂ -lower rough PBgI of S . Similarly, we can obtain the converse part. □

Theorem 5.4. *Let Ω be an IFPBgI of S . Then Ω is a ∂ -upper IRFPBgI of S if and only if for all $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2] \in D[0, 1]$ $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2)) \neq \phi$, and $(\Omega, (\lambda_1, \lambda_2))$ is a ∂ -upper rough PBgI of S .*

Proof. The proof is similar to Theorem 5.3 and follows from Theorem 2.1 we can obtain the proof easily. □

6. CONCLUSION

Fuzzy set theory and rough set theory take into account two distinct aspects of uncertainty that can be experienced in real world problems in many fields. The fusion of fuzzy set and rough set lead to various models. This paper is deliberated to built up a relation between rough sets, fuzzy sets and interval-valued fuzzy sets. In the present paper, we use Γ -semigroup instead of universe set, and introduced the notion of interval-valued rough fuzzy ideals, interval-valued fuzzy bi-ideals and interval-valued fuzzy prime ideals. Also, we believe, this paper will turn out to be more useful in the theory of rough sets and fuzzy sets.

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